

CULTURAL HERITAGE MANAGEMENT IN AKWA IBOM STATE: OVERCOMING THE 21ST CENTURY CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

Cultural heritage represents a vital link to the past and foundation for identity and continuity in communities across the world. In recent times, these assets have become the focus of conservation efforts and tourism interest. Despite huge potentials, high failure rates of heritage management projects have been reported in most settings. Safeguarding cultural assets for present and future generations require identifying opportunities, threats and innovative strategies. Management-related challenges such as poor financing practices, loss of assets, weak institutional frameworks, erosion of traditional practices and knowledge systems, and poor coordination with stakeholders have significantly affected the conservation, accessibility, and visibility of key heritage assets in a variety of settings. This study examined the current state of cultural heritage management in Akwa Ibom state, highlighted its challenges and proposed practical strategic intervention to overcome them. The study concludes that measures anchored in international best practices and adapted to local cultural and political contexts guarantee community participation, access to funding and sustainability of cultural assets.

Keywords: Community participation, Conservation, Cultural Properties, Heritage Management, Tourism

INTRODUCTION

Societies with rich cultural and historical landmarks boast of attractions capable of generating wealth, employment and revenue, and positioning them on the path to economic development (Comerio and Strozzi, 2019). Treasures such as heritage sites, monuments, and cultural rallies such as festivals and carnivals are formidable assets for the promotion of tourism in any society (Iniunam and Offong, 2020). The legacy handed down from the past, what is currently held dearly and what will be transmitted to the next generation are important components of tourism. Nigeria, as a culturally diverse country, is blessed with historical and cultural attractions. Different states of the federation have appealing physical artefacts, historical sites and cultural properties to showcase to the world. Akwa Ibom state, located in the coastal southern region, is highly endowed with destinations and practices which are historically, culturally and spiritually significant. These include slave warehouse, bridge of

no return, slave history museum, Ibibio museum, Annang heritage museum and Oron Museum. Deep-rooted traditional practices such as Ekpo masquerade, Atakpo, Ebre, Christmas village and Ibom heritage festivals are parts of the existing attractions.

While the oil industry still occupies front seat in the generation of income, heritage tourism is a potential area of investment. It is disheartening that despite the availability of these cultural and historical landmarks, the contribution of heritage tourism to the development of host communities is low especially when compared with the scorecards of other countries (Etuk, 2012). Scholars attribute this dismal performance to poor management practices (Dias *et al.*, 2018). Sadly, the state faces contemporary challenges in cultural heritage management because of environmental threats from oil exploration, urbanization and deterioration of cultural assets. As noted by Eken *et al.*, (2019), relics of culture are prone to decay and damage if not properly preserved. However, in a competitive environment where tourists are surrounded by travel options (Kamruzzaman *et al.*, 2020), it is crucial for stakeholders to package a destination, highlight its unique selling proposition and differentiate essentially from rivals (Hanna *et al.*, 2021; Leal *et al.*, 2022). Along this line, preserving these cultural assets guarantees not just the development of tourism industry as reported by Gu *et al.*, (2013) but also their long-term viability and huge revenue generation.

Even though Akwa Ibom state is blessed with fascinating sight and traditional practices, it has not commanded much attention from conservation stakeholders and researchers. There is paucity of scholarly publications on cultural heritage management in the study area. It is against this backdrop that the present study seeks to examine the challenges confronting heritage management in Akwa Ibom state and measures to tackle them.

Meaning and Functions of Cultural Heritage Management

Cultural heritage constitutes legacy, both tangible and intangible, bequeathed to a group or society by previous generations, and currently maintained in the present with a commitment to transmitting same to future generations (Bolin, 2019). Tangible resources considered part of cultural heritage include but not limited to sculpture, monuments, inscription, archaeological structure, and architectural works. Heritage is highly valued for its symbolic, instrumental, aesthetic and intellectual functions in society. Individuals and groups attach value to building, objects, place or events on account of age of the materials or practice, artistry, symbolism, association with a revered personality or feelings of affiliation derivable. One of the criteria used in labelling an object, place or event as heritage is the visual qualities they possess (UNESCO, 2007). In this way, cultural treasures such as building design, objects or site offer sensory experience and a sense of well-being to individuals. On the other hand, nonphysical cultural wealth includes customs, practices, expressions, representation, worship patterns and knowledge inherited from the previous generation, maintained by present society, and consciously transmitted to future generations. These are as attractive as structures and landmarks.

According to Tengberg *et al.*, (2012), what people attribute heritage value to constitute heritage. Values denote the worth of something (Kenter *et al.*, 2019). In the context of this study, heritage values refer to how significant heritage objects are (Diaz-Andreu, 2017). Across the world, places or events are known to command sacred meaning which are derived from either the belief or teachings of organized religion. These beliefs and teachings essentially define the spiritual identity of a group and offer insights to transcendental

experiences (Raymond *et al.*, 2019). In another instance, places or events are significant because of the beauty or inspiration they offer. Where practices, objects or sites evoke a sense of identity, belonging or association, scholars speak of social value. For example, Tengberg *et al.*, (2012) affirms that social value takes cognizance of the subjective meanings people attach to heritage and the imperativeness of community participation in its management.

The idea of cultural heritage management assumes that certain events, artistic design or objects have some underlying values which a community needs to leverage to its own benefit. As stated by UNESCO (2008), survival and sustainability of cultural heritage is contingent upon thoughtful management. It implies the application of management techniques to conserve cultural properties to ensure their long-term value and benefit. As noted by Hockings *et al.*, (2018), effective management in the context of cultural heritage has to do with quality of plans, measures and practices adopted in the protection of assets.

Heritage Management Approaches and Practices

The top-down approach was traditionally applied to the management of heritage sites (Sahraiyen and Turker, 2019). The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) adopted this approach based on categorization and assignment of legal meanings to heritage sites which are deemed outstanding. The strength of this approach lies in the support and media exposure enjoyed by sites listed by the organization (Maags, 2018). However, there are notable drawbacks. As noted by Alazaizeh *et al.*, (2016), this management approach ignores the roles of the various stakeholders in the sector. By neglecting individual voices and support of the community around heritage sites, this approach prioritizes practices that meet the interest of authorities and professionals (Escallon, 2020).

Value-based approach however, prioritizes stakeholders' interest and satisfaction. As stakeholders (for example private sector, public sector and users) are involved in the planning process, this management approach is otherwise known as stakeholder collaboration approach. It is about the involvement and empowerment of all the stakeholders in a way that enhances collaboration rather than conflict. The strength of this management approach lies in its emphasis on community engagement in key areas of concern including knowledge, perspectives and conservation practices. Despite its clear position on collaboration, the possibility of clash of value among stakeholder has been pointed out. Second, adopting this approach implies incurring extra cost in communication and planning (Imon, 2017).

The integrated heritage management approach brings together key considerations of different approaches in planning and decision making. For example, guidelines for heritage site management set up by UNESCO is integrative in nature. The success of cultural heritage destinations rests on the balance between heritage preservation and tourism. It focuses on protecting cultural heritage resources in ways that benefit the host communities and transmitting them to succeeding generations (Alazaizeh *et al.*, 2016).

Figure showing the differences between cultural heritage management approaches (Alazaizeh et al., 2016).

Heritage Sites Management Challenges

Several key cultural heritage sites across the world face significant management challenges, some of which are discussed in this study. These challenges are categorized as human threat or natural risks in the heritage management literature. First, buildings linked to historic events are falling into disrepair because of poor management practices (Berhanu, 2018). Cultural heritage sites are also known to suffer from low patronage due to poor financing practices and insufficient preservation efforts. Also in the list are improper handling of system, improper project selection, erroneous policies, corrupt practices and poor coordination with stakeholders (Sinamai, 2018). The problems associated with lack of policies or ineffectiveness in their implementation have been elaborated in the work of Osman (2018) conducted in Egypt. Generally, there is consensus among scholars that these challenges culminate to the deterioration of cultural assets (Irandu and Shah, 2016).

Non-tangible treasures such as ekpo masquerade, an integral part of Ibibio, Annang, and Efik cultures, are at risk due to modernization, religious opposition, and lack of documentation. This problem underscores the threat posed to cultural properties by negative attitude of people. As observed by Mancacaritadipura (2007), the tendency for young people to disregard their local culture in favour of Western lifestyle is high. Lack of respect on the part of locals towards their cultural treasures hampers cultural preservation efforts. Furthermore, it is reported that attractive sites in some African settings remain unprotected and neglected, leaving it susceptible to decay and damage. For example, it is reported (Benali and Chennaoui, 2017; Eyo (2018) that artefacts in awe-inspiring locations in a variety of settings are deteriorating due to managerial deficiency and insufficient funding. On the other hand, modern global challenges such as climate change, rising sea levels and flooding are among the natural risk factors (Ciambrone, 2016). In the face of these challenges, scholars aver that conservation and sustainable safeguarding of cultural properties are hinged on effective management (Cesaro *et al.*, 2023).

OVERCOMING CULTURAL HERITAGE MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES IN AKWAIBOM STATE

Cultural heritage management in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, encounters numerous challenges which include funding constraints, environmental degradation, and weak institutional frameworks. Others are erosion of traditional practices and knowledge systems, and poor coordination with stakeholders. These challenges have significantly affected the conservation, accessibility, and visibility of key heritage assets such as the Bridge of No Return and the Ekpo masquerade tradition (Eyo, 2018).

To address these issues, management approaches anchored in international best practices and adapted to local cultural and political contexts are imperative. First, strengthening the legal and institutional frameworks is crucial. Many cultural properties such as Ekpo masquerade, Atakpo, Ebre, Christmas village and Ibom heritage festivals in the state are yet to receive formal recognition or protection under national heritage legislation. Integrating them into Nigeria's official register of protected cultural properties, supported by state-level legislation, would provide a legal basis for safeguarding and ultimately conservation (UNESCO, 2013; Ndoro & Wijesuriya, 2015). In view of this, it is crucial for the state government to develop and implement laws that formally recognize and protect both tangible and intangible cultural assets. This measure is in consonance with Zhang (2022), that laws of a state are the basis for effective management of heritage. An agency, hopefully, Akwa Ibom State Heritage Management Agency, should be created within the state Ministry of Culture and Tourism to coordinate documentation, preservation projects, research, community engagement, and collaboration with national bodies like the National Commission for Museums and Monuments.

Second, community participation and ownership must be at the core of heritage management efforts. Smith (2006) averred that heritage management is not merely about preserving monuments but about sustaining living traditions and cultural meanings embedded in communities. Involving local stakeholders such as custodians of Ekpo traditions, traditional rulers, and youth groups not only ensures sustainable management but also guarantees intergenerational transmission of knowledge and practices (UNESCO, 2003). As continued existence and sustainability of these treasures largely depend on this participatory approach, it is crucial for indigenous custodians, traditional institutions, and local artisans to be effectively engaged in heritage resources management in the state.

Third, capacity building is critical for effective heritage management. As already noted, many heritage sites in Akwa Ibom lack the technical expertise and institutional support crucial for effective management. There is an urgent need for training programs in areas such as preventive conservation, digital documentation, and museum management. Partnership working with local institutions, universities, and relevant international organizations can help bridge these gaps (Ndoro & Wijesuriya, 2015). Stakeholders should prioritize training programs for museum staff, local scholars, and cultural stakeholders should be prioritized.

Fourth, managing cultural heritage treasures and transmitting them to succeeding generations require adequate funding. Sufficient capital is required to run conservation and tourism endeavours. As government funding is often limited and irregular, collaborative working with actors in the private sector and non-governmental organizations can provide additional resources. Furthermore, as local and international tourists demonstrate great interest in visiting historical and cultural heritage sites, the potentials for heritage tourism in the state should be given adequate attention. Harnessing saleable cultural tourism products

that include local museums, colonial relics, and traditional festivals can play dual functions of generating revenue while promoting heritage awareness (Timothy & Nyaupane, 2009). In view of this, it is crucial to Integrate heritage tourism into the economic development strategy of the state.

Lastly, public education and awareness campaigns are crucial management capabilities. Many citizens, especially the younger generation, are not aware of the value of local heritage assets. Embedding cultural heritage studies into formal education and launching targeted campaigns through schools, media, and cultural events can help instill a heritage-consciousness among citizens which will translate to burning commitment to protect these resources (Eyo, 2018; Ndoro & Wijesuriya, 2015). Similarly, digital inventories of both tangible and intangible assets should be developed. This will enhance their preservation and increases public visibility via online platforms.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the challenges and critical success factors in the management of cultural properties in Akwa Ibom state. It highlighted that the existence of cultural treasures in a location does not guarantee its continuous availability and tourists' interest. The survival and wide appreciation of cultural resources depend largely on effective management. Despite wide acceptance of heritage management as it relates to Sustainable Development Goal, there are impediments to actualizing the balance between development and preservation. While natural risk factors such as rising sea levels and flooding have been found to hamper heritage conservation efforts, issues related to managerial capacity have been identified in the study. Partnership working with stakeholders such as local institutions, and relevant international organizations is the route to building capacity and accessing necessary funding. Public education and awareness campaigns are crucial success factors in management of cultural properties. Promoting heritage awareness is considered crucial management strategy as it instills a heritage-consciousness and burning commitment to protect these resources, and ultimately positioning host communities on the path to economic development through heritage tourism.

REFERENCES

- Alazaizah, M. Hallo, J., BackMan, S. Norman, W. and Vogel, M. (2016). Value Orientation and Heritage Tourism Management at Petra Archaeological Park, *Jordan Tourism Management*, 57, 149 – 158.
- Benali, L. and Chennatui, Y. (2017). The Archaeological Site of Tipasa, Algeria: What Kind of Management Plan? *Conserv. Mang. Archaeol. Site*, 19, 173 – 196.
- Berhanu, E. (2018). Potentials and Challenges of Religious Tourism Development in Lalibela, Ethiopia. *African J Hosp. Tour Leis*; 7(4): 1-17.
- Mancacaritadipura, G. (2007). Safeguarding the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Indonesia: Systems, Schemes, Activities and Problem. In the 30th International Symposium on the Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Property, Japan.
- Bolin, A. (2019). Imagining Genocide Heritage: Material Modes of Development and Preservation in Rwanda. *J Mater Cult*.
- Camerio, N and Strozzi, F. (2019). Tourism and its economic impact: A literature review using bibliometric tools. *Tourism Economics* 25(4): 135481661879376.
- Cesaro, G., Jamhawi, M., Al – Tahar, H., Farajat, I, Orbasli, A. (2023). A Learning from

- Practices: The Integrated \management Plan for Petra World Heritage Site in Jordan. *J. Herit. Mang.* 8, 125 – 141.
- Ciambrone, A. (2016). Instarbal World Heritage Property: Representating the Complexity of its Management Plan. In *Proceedings of the World Heritage and Degradation Smart Design, Planning and Technologies*, Naples, Italy, 16 – 18; 1 – 10.
- Diaz – Andriell, M. (2017). Heritage Values and the Public. *Journal of Community Archaeology and Heritage*, 4(1), 2-6.
- Diaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Martin-Lopez, B. Watson, R., Molnar, Z., Hill, R., Chan, K Baste, I Brauman, K. Polasky, S., Church, A., Consdale M., Larigauderie, A. Leadley P. Van Oudenhoven, A. Vander Plaat, F., Schroter, M., Laord, S. and Schirayama, Y. (2018). Assessing nature's Contributions to People: Recognizing Culture, and Diverse Sources of Knowledge, can Improve Assessments *Science*, 359(6373), 270-272.
- Eken, E., Tasci, B. and Gustafsson, C. (2019). An evaluation of decision-making process on maintenance of built cultural heritage: The case of Visby Sweden. *Cities*, 94: 24-32.
- Escallon, M. (2020). Negotiating Intangibles: The Power, Place and Prestige of NIGOs in Heritage Governance. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 26, 719 – 736
- Etuk, E. (2012). 'Marketing of Tourism Services in Nigeria: A study with special refence to Cross River State; *Marketing Journal of National Institute of Marketing of Nigeria*, 1(1).
- Eyo, E. (2018). Sustaining aspects of cultural heritage management in Nigeria: Case study of wooden objects in the National Museum in Oron. *European American Journals*. Retrieved from <https://www.eajournals.org>
- Gu, Y., Du, J., Qiao, X., Bossard, C., Deny, G. (2013). Challenges for sustainable tourism at the Jiuzhaigou world heritage site in Western China. *Nat. Resour. Forum*, 37, 103-112.
- Hanna, S., Jennifer, R., and Brendan, K. (2021). Place and Destination Branding: A Review and Conceptual Mapping of the Domain. *European Management Review* 18: 105-17.
- Hockings, M., James, R. Stolen, S., Dudtey, N., Mathur, V., Markombo, J, Courreu J. Parrish, J. (2018). *Enhancing Our Heritage Toolkit: Assessing Management Effectiveness of Natural World Heritage Sites*. UNESCO: Paris, France, 1 – 108.
- Imon, S. (2017). Cultural heritage management under tourism pressure. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*. 9 (3), 335-348.
- Iniunam, U. and Offong, S. (2020). Sustainable Tourism Resources Management and Socio-economic Development of Nigeria. *Ripples of Culture Journal of Anthropology*, (1): 103-111.
- Irandu, E. and Shah P. (2016) Development of Cultural Heritage Forum in Kenya: A Strategy for Diversification of Tourism Products. *Conservation of National and Cultural Heritage in Kenya. A Cross-Disciplinary Approach*; 154-171.
- Kamruzzaman, M., Farjana, S. and Khandker, N. (2020). Travel Behaviour in Brisbane: Trends, Saturation, Patterns and Changes. *Transformation Research Part A Policy and Practice* 140: 231-50.
- Kenter, J., Raymond, C., Van Riper, C., Calgni, E., Christie, I., Chritie, M., Fordham, A., Gould, R., Ives, C., Hejnowicz, A., Gunton, R. Horcea – Mucu, A., Kendal, D., Kronenberg, J., Massenberg, J., O'Connor, s., Ravenscroft, N., and Thankappan, S. (2019). Loving the Wess: Navigating Diversity and Conflict in Social Values for Sustainability. *Sustainability Science*, 14(5), 1439-1461.
- Leal, M., Beatriz, C. and Joao, F. (2022). Tourism Co-creation in place branding: The role of

- local community. *Tourism Review* 77: 1322-32
- Maags, C. (2018). Creating a Race to the Top: Hierarchies and Competition within the Chinese ICH Transmitters System. In C Maags, and M. Svensson (Eds.) *Chinese Heritage in the Making: Experiences, Negotiation, and Contestations*. Amsterdam University Press.
- Ndoro, W., & Wijesuriya, G. (2015). *Heritage Management and Conservation: From Colonization to Globalization*. ICCROM.
- Osman, A. (2018). Heritage Conservation Management in Egypt. A review of the Current and Proposed Situation to amend it. *Ain Shams Eng. J.*, 9, 2907 – 2916
- Raymon, C., Kenfer, J. van Riper, C. Rawluk, A., and Kendal, D. (2019). Editorial Overview: Theoretical Traditions in Social Values for Sustainability. *Sustainability Science*, 14(5), 1173-1185.
- Sahraiyani, F. and Turker, O. (2019). Values-based Framework for Prioritizing Conservation of Heritage Buildings for Tourism. In *value of Heritage for Tourism*. Retrieved from https://ees.kuleuven.be/unit-win_2019/proceedings/proceedings_unitwin_2019-sahraiyanjahromi.pdf.
- Sinamai, A. (2018). African Cultural Heritage Conservation and Mangement: Theory and Practice from Southern Africa. *Conservation Management Archaeology Safes*: 20(1): 52-4.
- Smith, L. (2006). *Uses of Heritage*. London: Routledge.
- Timothy, D. J., & Nyaupane, G. P. (2009). *Cultural Heritage and Tourism in the Developing World: A Regional Perspective*. London: Routledge.
- Tengberg, A., Fredholm, S. Eliasson, I. Knez I., Saltzman, K, and Wetterberg, O. (2012). Cultural Ecosystem Services provided by Landscapes: Assessment of Heritage Values and Identity. *Ecosystem Services*, 2, 14-26.
- UNESCO (2003). *Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage*. Retrieved from: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/convention>.
- UNESCO. (2007). *Climate Change and World Heritage: Report on Predicting and Managing the Impacts of Climate Change on World Heritage and Strategy to Assist States Parties to Implement Appropriate Management Resources*. Retrieved from UNESCO – World Heritage Convention: http://whc.unesco.org/documents/public_wh_paper_22_en.pdf.
- UNESCO. (2013). *Managing Cultural World Heritage*. Paris: UNESCO World Heritage Centre.
- Zhang, S. (2022). The Development and Institutional Characteristics of China's Built Heritage Conservation Legislation. *Built. Herit*, 6, 11.